

A312

26 JAN 94

FLIGHT FOLDER

GMT

DATE: 26 / 01 / 94 TAKE OFF 122703 H (local time) FLIGHT NO. A 312
LANDING 185319

IPIECA OPERATING OUT OF LAS PALMAS, GRAN CANARIA

PROJECT OFFICER: A KAYE
AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A KAYE
FLIGHT LEADER: D. LAUCHLAN
OBSERVER:
OTHERS:

CAPTAIN: H. BURGoyNE
CO-PILOT: G. DELMEGE
NAVIGATOR: E. HEATON
ENGINEER: K. QUICK
LOADMASTER: J. CANNING

VACC: COLIN O'DOWD
2D: M. PICKERING
CCN/FILTERS: D. PERCIVAL

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (s):
OPERATING AREA: WEST OF THE CANARY ISLANDS

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME:

A312 26-JAN-94

GPS data
11:47:07 - 18:56:57

Flight Report : A312 26-01-1994

122703 Take Off Las Palmas, Gran Canaria.

132129(5) - 134300(7)	Profile P1	FL160-50'	285°	SS=4/5
134407(8) - 134609(9)	Run 1.1	100'	240°	QNH=1029
134950(10) - 135211(11)	Run 1.2	100'	60°	K-Gamma
135449(12) - 135951(13)	Run 2.1	100'	240°	K-Gamma
155951(13) - 140421(14)	Run 2.2	100'	240°	
140645(15) - 141146(16)	Run 2.3	100'	150°	
141146(16) - 141706(17)	Run 2.4	100'	150°	
142058(18) - 142558(19)	Run 3.1	2100'	340°	
142258(19) - 143025(20)	Run 3.2	2100'	340°	
143433(21) - 143933(22)	Run 3.3	2100'	065°	
143933(23) - 144524(25)	Run 3.4	2100'	065°	
145008(26) - 145252(27)	Run 4.1	2200'	150°	
145330(28) - 145923(29)	Run 4.2	2100'	330°	
150222(30) - 150533(31)	Run 4.3	3100'	165°	
150901(32) - 151219(33)	Run 4.4	5600'	330°	
151423(34) - 151800(35)	Run 5.1	5400'	220°	
152131(36) - 152431(37)	Run 5.2	3800'	030°	
152730(38) - 153023(39)	Run 5.3	2200'	210°	
153345(40) - 153636(41)	Run 5.4	2200'	035°	
154032(42) - 154429(43)	Run 6.1	6600'	225°	
154815(44) - 155116(45)	Run 6.2	5900'	040°	
155453(46) - 155737(47)	Run 6.3	4200'	230°	
160049(48) - 160412(50)	Run 6.4	2300'	050°	
160746(52) - 161123(53)	Run 6.5	2400'	230°	
163000(55) - 163500(56)	Run 7.1	8000'	335°	
163500(56) - 163827(57)	Run 7.2	8000'	335°	
164303(58) - 164806(59)	Run 7.3	8000'	065°	
164806(59) - 165314(60)	Run 7.4	8000'	065°	
165642(61) - 165900(62)	Run 8.1	5000'	205°	
170249(63) - 170528(64)	Run 8.2	3700'	025°	
170911(65) - 171220(66)	Run 8.3	2700'	210°	
171538(67) - 171848(68)	Run 8.4	2700'	020°	

172211 - 173740 Profile P2 50'-FL115 090° QNH=1028

SS=4/5

185319 Land at Las Palmas, Gran Canaria.

A312

26 January 1994

Aircraft Scientists summary

Synoptic Conditions:

It was decided to fly to the South-West of the Canary Islands to the region dominated by the High pressure area towards the Azores.

Flight Summary:

For all intents and purposes this flight was a duplicate of yesterday's flight.

We found some excellent fields of small Cu, and studied four clouds in detail with reciprocal runs. The Cu were generally found in rows so runs through the clouds in one direction only were practical.

The aircraft scientist did not concentrate on note taking during the active part of the flight, but dictated his notes onto the PA channel which is recorded on the flight Video.

SORTIE BRIEF: 26 JANUARY 1994

IPIECA/VACC

- 1) SORTIE OBJECTIVE:** To study the micro-physical and radiative properties of small precipitating cumulus clouds and the influence of marine aerosol on cloud micro-physics.
- 2) LOCATION:**
- 3) WEATHER:** Field of moderate cumulus clouds.
- 4) FLIGHT PATTERN:**
 - a.** Transit to operating area at suitable altitude.
 - b.** Execute a profile from Fl 150 to 50ft in cloud free air, if possible, @ 1000ft/min down to general cloud top then profile @ 500ft/min (30min)
 - c.** Conduct a K-GAMMA wind field calibration (5min)
 - d.** Conduct L-shaped along wind @ 100ft above sea-level and 100ft below cloud base. These runs will also be used for VACC runs. Call 2 runs on each leg, with outside MRF turn at corner.
 - e.** If cloud is large enough and not effected by aircraft, conduct 3 figure-of-8 (centered on the cloud one leg parallel to wind and one leg perpendicular to the wind.) Leg length needs to be about 10 miles. At levels to be determined by the aircraft scientist (nominally 300 ft below cloud top, mid-cloud level and 100ft above cloud-base.)

If clouds are not distinct enough to perform above pattern, repeat L patterns at levels to be advised within the cloud layer.
 - f.** If cloud is apparently unchanged, repeat e. upto twice more, centered on the same cloud. If the cloud decays (or disappears...) repeat e. using another cloud.
 - g.** Conduct L-shaped run above cloud top, level to be given by aircraft scientist.
 - h.** Profile from 50ft at 500ft/min to cloud top and then transit back to base.

TOTAL DURATION

Spanish diplomatic clearance required.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: IPIECA/VACC Date: 26/1/94

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye

Flight No: A312 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:47:35	00	TRANZ	15.8	P	275	27.79	-16.55		
12:57:12	00	TRANZ	15.8	P	272	27.82	-17.67	1/8 cu 2/8 sc - clouds over the islands clear above.	
13:16:36	00	TRANZ	15.9	P	273	27.25	-19.98	4/8 sc Below with clusters of small cu in gaps.	
13:21:29	01	P1	16.0	P	274	27.25	-20.17	tops of clouds 8000ft.	
								cloud tops 5900ft.	
13:42:59	07	P1	500ft	R	271	27.25	-21.66	1029 sea state 4.5 3/8 cu some sc ahead right) - 2000 old base	
13:44:66	08	R2.1	100ft	R	230	27.21	21.74		
13:44:66									
13:54:48	12	R2.1	100ft	R	228	27.14	-21.76	2/8 small cu. 1359 ZC R2.2 started.	
14:03:51								air temp change 5 min ago and three before that on this leg - matching PctSP changes.	
14:06:45	15	R2.3	100ft	R	134	26.78	-22.19	2/8 cu / 14:11:46 end 2.3 -> begin 2.4 clouds are at sparser at the end of the leg.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye.

Project: IPIECA/NAACL Date: 26/1/94

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:17:06	17	R2.4	100ft.	K	137	26.39	21.85 -21.85	5/8 sc turning back towards Cu.	
14:20:58	18	R3.1	2100ft	P	326	26.39	-21.88	Starting run in precipitating cloud <u>2200</u> 14:25:57.	
14:30:24	20	R3.2 ^{end}	2100	P	331	26.79	-22.25	4/8 Cu looks like a good area for clouds -	
14:30-16	25							AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST JAT IN CUPOLA WATCHING THE CLOUD BEING STUDIED AND LOGGING COMMENTARY PA.	
16:26:29	54		8000	P				4/8 cu with thin stratus along the top.	
16:29:57	55		8000	P	329	26.41	-21.89	2/8 cu below with stratus sheet to left clear above.	
16:42:01	57					26.80	-22.31	field of small Cu with stratus sheet to west.	
16:43:02	58	R7.3	8000	P	50	26.80	-22.20	5/8 cu below clear above. 16:48:00 change to R74	
								Aircraft Scientist in cupola logging 4th cloud PA.	
17:18:49	68	6.4	2700	P	32	27.24	-21.95	5/8 cu above.	
17:22:13	69	P2	50ft	R	77	27.20	-21.72	3/8 cu above. Sea state 4-5 Pressure 1028	
								cloud base - 2200 ft.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: *IP/ECA/VACE* Date: *26/1/94*

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
						<i>17:52:45</i>	<i>70</i>		
<i>17:37:46</i>		<i>P2</i>	<i>11500</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>85</i>	<i>27.36</i>	<i>-20.84</i>	<i>3/8 Cu below some small areas of Sc.</i>	

17:22
30
17:52

26-01-94

IRTECA

D PERCIVAL

GMT	ALLEV.		Height	Dyn	STATIC							REMARKS	
	On	Off			1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
100410													S PRE FLT
	/												S
100610		/	GRND										D Power Surge
													B Inst crashes
													R
					1024.5								P 1024.5
				7	77N	1	2	3	4	5	6		
124909	/		F4160	108	0.04	0.11	0.22	0.32	0.43	0.57	0.89	S	Asst takeoff
125105		/		46	305	287	289		288	290	365	D	F4160
				240	307	291	291	291	306	302	292	B	
				252	2510	2523	2525	2526	2530	2526	2526	R	
				943	943.8	942.7	942.7	943.2	943.5	943.8	943.6	P	
135526	/		1000ft	1011	0.11	0.22	0.31	0.43	0.56	0.89	1.08	S	R2-1
135640		/	L	590	461	339	322	322	342	456	535	D	R2-1
			pattern	530	466	361	311	306	305	304	304	B	
				2522	2522	2521	2520	2529	2523	2530	2528	R	
				1023.2	1023.1	1023.1	1023.0	1022.5	1023.0	1012.5	1012.3	P	
140744	/			1.11	0.11	0.22	0.31	0.43	0.57	0.89	1.07	S	
140908		/	1000ft	3546	344	309	314	345	357	488	674	D	R2-3
			L pattern	308	304	299	302	302	297	301	302	B	
				2535	2531	2524	2524	2523	2514	2515	2515	R	
				1022.2	1022.0	1021.7	1022.5	1021.5	1022.4	1018	1000	P	
142115	/		2100ft	1.09	0.11	0.21	0.31	0.42	0.52	0.87	1.06	S	Cloud
142233		/		367	322	331	372	377	352	513	611	D	Base
				291	289	288	286	289	304	305	292	B	R3-1
				2527	2527	2529	2530	2533	2535	2535	2534	R	
				952.7	952.3	951.2	951.7	952.1	952	950	953.1	P	
143440	/		2100	1.06	0.10	0.21	0.31	0.43	0.55	0.87	1.06	S	Cloud
143550		/		333	352	307	327	347	366	443	596	D	Base
				289	289	284	287	302	303	303	287	B	Run 3-3
				2545	2542	2540	2541	2537	2535	2537	2531	R	
				952.3	952.5	952.5	953.0	952.4	953.3	951.8	911.5	P	
145030	/		2200	1.09								S	Cloud Base
145142		/		310								D	1100
				291								B	R4-1
				2534								R	DYNAMIC
				951.6								P	ONLY

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SEZ.	CONC/CC	MAX SEZ.	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SEZ.	CONC/1.	MAX SEZ.	
1232										20 ON.
125200	15	05								
130000	20	01								
131000	26	05								
132130	25	05								Start PI from FL160
132232	35	05								FL150
132337	40	05								FL140
132446	28	10								FL130
132542	30	10								FL120
132639	25	10								FL110
132730	20	10								FL100
132830	15	05								FL90
132930	30	15		5						FL80
133100	35	10								FL70
133255	12	05		5						FL60 (50/1cc between levels (once))
133450	35	3	0.1	10						FL50
133630	120	25	0.1	10						FL40
133800	160	25	0.2	15						FL30
133943	75	25	0.1	15						FL20
134110	35	3	0.1	15						1000'
134300	35	3	0.2	15						end of P
134405										Start K - Gamma Run Part 1
134500	50	3	0.1	10						
134605										end of Run.
134945										Start K - Gamma Run Part 2.
135000	75	25	0.1	15						
135205										end of Run.

* DRS TIME

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R eff	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	
135449										Start Run 2.1 @ 100'
135500	35	3	0.2	15						
135700	60	3	0.2	15						
135900	110	3	0.2	15						
135950										end of Run. and start Run 2.2 @ 100'
140000	130	3	0.3	15						
140200	130	3	0.3	15						
140400	95	3	0.2	15						
140420										end of Run
140642										Start Run 2.3
140700	100	3	0.3	15						
140900	130	3	0.3	15						
141100	140	3	0.2	15						
141144										end of Run & start Run 2.4 @ 100'
141200	156	3	0.1	15						
141400	150	3	0.1	15						
141600	160	3	0.3	15						
141705										end of Run
142056										Start Run 3.1 @ 2100
142100	180	3	0.5	35		5	80			
142300	140	3	0.6	30		6	500			
142500	140	3	0.3	15						
142600										end of Run 3.1 and start Run 3.2
142800	140	3	0.2	15						
143000	120	3	0.4	15						
143022										end of Run
143431										Start Run 3.3

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
143500	130	3	0.4	15						
143700	110	3	0.4	20						
143900	90	3	0.4	15						
143932										end of Run & start Run 3.4
144100	70	3	0.4	20						
144300	70	3	0.1	15						
144500										end of Run
145000	80	3	0.2	10						Start Run 4.1
145107	600	3	200	35	10	10	75			cloud
145250										end of Run
145500	70	3	0.6	20		0.5				Start Run 4.2
145700	350	3	10	35	9	10	75			cloud
145900										end of Run
150000	100	3	0.1	15						Start Run 4.3 @ 3100'
150354	8000	3	350	40	12.5	30	75			cloud
150533										end of Run
150900	45	15	0.05	10						Start Run 4.4 @ 5600'
151035	1600	3	300	40	14	1000	225			cloud
151221										end of Run
151423	70	3	0.05	10						Start Run 5.1
151620	2000	3	100	35	14	400	200			
151804										end of Run
152135	100	3	0.1	20						Start Run 5.2
152241	1000	3	350	35	12	50	100			
152620										end of Run
152729	90	3	0.4	15						Start Run 5.3 2200'
152840	3000	3	300	30	8					

* DRS TIME

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	R #	CONCL	MAX SIZ.	CONC/L	MAX SIZ.	
153023										end of Run
153345	180	3	0.2	20						Start Run 5.4
153449	600	3	3.4	30	8	5	100			Cloud
153635										end of Run
154631	95	1.5								Start Run 6.1 @ 6600'
154257	2000	3	0.50	40	13	1000	125			Cloud
154428										end of Run
154812	60	3	0.05	15						Start Run 6.2 @ 6900'
154940	1400	3	0.50	40	12	700	175			Cloud
155118										end of Run
155455	100	3	0.1	15						Start Run 6.3 @ 4200'
155550	800	3	2.0	35	11	90	150			Cloud
155735										end of Run
160050	110	3	0.4	15						Start Run 6.4 @ 2300'
160227	400	3	3.5	35	9	10				Cloud
160411										end of Run
160744	100	3	0.3	20						Start Run 6.5 @ 2600'
160858	800	3	3.5	30	9	10	100			Cloud
161124	↑									end of Run
162958										Start Run 7.1 @ 5000'
163100	30	1.5	0.02	5						
163300	35	2	0.02	5						
163500	30	2.5	0.02	5						end of Run & Start Run 7.2 @ 5000'
163700	25	2	0.01	5						
163827										end of Run
164300										Start Run 7.3 @ 3000'
164400	25	1	0.01	5						

* DRS TIME

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONCL	MAX SIZE	
164600	25	25	001	10						
164500										end of Run & start Run 74
164900	25	25	001	5						
165100	23	2	005	10						
165315										end of Run
165640	70	2	03	15						Start Run 8.1 ~ 5300'
165700	2000	3	150	40	B	800	800			cloud
165859										end of Run
170267	80	3	02	15						Start Run 8.2 ~ 3700'
170350	900	3	30	35	12	100	200			cloud
170528										end of Run
170911	80	3	02	25						Start Run 8.3 ~ 2800'
171043	350	3	25	35	10	5	600			cloud
171220										end of Run
171536	90	3	01	20						Start Run 8.4
171714	100	3	30	30	7	3				
171821										end of Run
172212	50	3	0.1	10						Start 12 ton 50'
172402	60	3	0.2	15						1000'
172555	65	25	0.2	20						2000'
172730	70	3	0.1	15						3000'
172903	55	25	0.1	10						4000'
173041	35	3	0.1	15						5000'
173210	30	1	0.02	10						6000'
173320	15	3	0.01	5						7000'
173414	30	3								8000'
173511	6	05								9000'

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GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R eff	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC%/l	MAX SIZE	
173554	18	0.5								10000'
173711	13	0.5								FL110
173740	17	0.5								FL110 ↗ end of P

* DRS TIME

A312 26-JAN-94 12:42:00 000 Ω 27.75 -15.94 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
277.	616.	13.1	263.	-5.8	-22.6	086/23

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A312 26-JAN-94 13:45:00 008 Ω 27.18 -21.77 AS P

HDG degT	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
229.	1026.	-0.3	185.	17.3	c 11.8	059/ 9

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A312

26-JAN-94

13:46:54

009

Ω .27.13 -21.87

AS P

HDG degT 312.	SPR mb 1018.	PHGT kft -0.1	TAS knots 180.	TAT C 16.4	DEW C 12.3	WIND deg m/s 052/9
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SPR
mb

1018.26

PHGTF
Kft

-0.14

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A312 26-JAN-94 17:39:06 071 Ω 27.36 -20.77 AS P

HDG deg T	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
87.	614.	13.2	240.	-5.7	-21.0	094/41

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A312 26-JAN-94 17:50:33 071 Ω 27.43 -19.96 AS P

HDG	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
degT	mb	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s
76.	531.	16.8	313.	-12.1	c-44.3	093/70

GE DP

FWVS DP

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

062

16
11 Σ

Max 19.2
Min 15.0

DATA TIME: 261500 JAN 1994
SCALE 1: 6 560 000 UK AND CANARIES
DATA CUTOFF TIME : 16:00

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE
Meteorological Research Flight

Fax to: MET RESEARCH C-130

Fax No: 0103428574261

Fax from: MARK

Date/Time: 26/0815

Pages: 4 Including this

0800Z IR

Bu
Tel:
Fa

UK
88

TIME: 250000 12 JAN 94

mb	Dev	WIND
MAX WINDS: MLL		
150	310	27
202	310	27
203	350	25
303	345	30
361	350	28
432	350	24
517	350	18
617	030	18
721	030	20
817	050	22
837	040	24
910	070	19
1005	050	12
1028	055	10

Parts: A C D missing

No hodograph shown for forecast ascent

35°N 10.0W
 T+12 VT 12Z
 26/01/94

STATION: 80020		
SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE-		
TIME: 260000		JAN 94
mb	Deg	Kts
MAX WINDS		
362	090	01
100	285	22
150	308	26
200	340	13
250	078	47
300	075	50
400	080	57
500	070	42
700	070	44
850	045	21
925	023	18
1000	019	14
SURFACE	310	8
Part :	P. mapping	

SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE
26/00Z ACTUAL

HODOGRAPH for 80020 at 260000 ONLY

A312 26-JAN-94 Height time series

Run P1 13:21:29-13:43:00 GMT

Run R1.1 13:44:07-13:46:09 GMT

Run R1.2 13:49:50-13:52:11 GMT

Run R2.1 13:54:49-13:59:51 GMT

Run R2.3 14:06:45–14:11:46 GMT

Run R2.4 14:11:46–14:17:06 GMT

Run R3.1 14:20:58–14:25:58 GMT

Run R3.2 14:22:58–14:30:25 GMT

Run R3.3 14:34:33–14:39:33 GMT

Run R3.4 14:39:33–14:45:24 GMT

Run R4.1 14:50:08–14:52:52 GMT

Run R4.2 14:53:30–14:59:23 GMT

Run R4.3 15:02:22–15:05:33 GMT

Run R4.4 15:09:01–15:12:19 GMT

Run R5.1 15:14:23–15:18:00 GMT

Run R5.2 15:21:31–15:24:31 GMT

Run R5.3 15:27:30–15:30:23 GMT

Run R5.4 15:33:45–15:36:36 GMT

Run R6.1 15:40:32–15:44:29 GMT

Run R6.2 15:48:15–15:51:16 GMT

Run R6.3 15:54:53–15:57:37 GMT

Run R6.4 16:00:49–16:04:12 GMT

Run R6.5 16:07:46–16:11:23 GMT

Run R7.1 16:30:00–16:35:00 GMT

Run R7.2 16:35:00–16:38:27 GMT

Run R7.3 16:43:03–16:48:06 GMT

Run R7.4 16:48:06–16:53:14 GMT

Run R8.1 16:56:42–16:59:00 GMT

Run R8.2 17:02:49–17:05:28 GMT

Run R8.3 17:09:11–17:12:20 GMT

Run R8.4 17:15:38–17:18:48 GMT

Run P2 17:22:11–17:37:40 GMT

